

Experimental Investigation on Concrete by Partial Replacement of Cement with Dolomite and Coarse Aggregate with Broken Ceramic Tiles

Arunkumar K K^{1*} and Ninumol Das²

¹*Department of Civil Engineering*

SCMS Institute of Multidisciplinary Studies, Perumbavoor, Kerala, India

²*Engineering professional, Perumbavoor, Kerala, India*

Abstract

When it comes to building materials, the most commonly used material is concrete. Production of concrete and its ingredients results in substantial emission of greenhouse gases. The method of extracting and processing the basic ingredients for concrete reduce the amount of non-renewable resources, harm the natural environment and creates an ecological imbalance. Here we are conducting an experiment in concrete by partially replacing its ingredients by waste materials and low-cost items in different ratios and strength test is conducted after 28 days curing. An optimum ratio is determined which gives greater strength than normal mix which will help to reduce the environmental impact and also give a successful method for waste management.

Keywords- concrete, compressive strength, aggregates, experimental investigation, concrete testing, partial replacement, dolomite, ceramic tiles

1. Introduction

The one that's most frequently utilized building material in the construction sector is concrete. Cement, water, fine and coarse aggregates, and aggregates are the raw components used in typical concrete. Cement production accounts for 4–5% of global CO₂ emissions.[1] 500 - 900 kg of CO₂ is generated with each tonne of cement produced.[2] The raw materials extraction results in landscape degradation. Dust and greenhouse gases are released during the factory's raw material processing stages which will contaminate the environment and aggravate climate change.[3][4] The increasing demand for cement and concrete will necessitate the development of strategies to lessen their environmental impact. Successful adoption of substitute materials, whose production is more economical, requires fewer natural resources, and has a smaller environmental impact, will eventually give rise to a greener and healthier environment for future generations. As a result, there is an increased interest in developing environmentally acceptable alternatives to conventional concrete. One such alternative is the partial replacement of coarse aggregate with ceramic tiles and cement with dolomite in concrete.

Cement can be partially replaced with dolomite, a mineral that is extracted from sedimentary rock beds. Incorporating waste tile aggregate in place of coarse aggregate aids in minimizing waste and lessens overexploitation. There is good enough tile waste on

the planet to utilize it as an aggregate in concrete. Tile is made by sintering natural materials at high temperatures. The tile is free of dangerous chemicals. Waste tiles do nothing other than pollution. The properties of coarse aggregate made from ceramic waste is quite similar to those of aggregates used in the manufacturing of concrete. The characteristics of ceramic waste coarse aggregate fall comfortably within the range of values seen in aggregates used in concrete production.[5] There is little to no difference between the characteristics of normal concrete and ceramic waste coarse aggregate concrete.[6] Ceramic waste coarse aggregate concrete has gained popularity due to its numerous advantages over conventional cementation materials. It has two benefits: first, it can stop the depletion of finite natural resources; second, it can shield various utilized materials from serious environmental risks.

There are many advantages to using ceramic tiles and dolomite in concrete. First, it reduces the amount of cement required for concrete production, which in turn reduces carbon dioxide emissions. Second, it reduces the amount of waste generated by the construction industry by using waste materials such as dolomite and ceramic tiles. Finally, it enhances the concrete's mechanical properties, including durability and compressive strength.

Numerous investigations have previously been performed by partially substituting the cement in concrete with dolomite powder, and the results have become highly successful [15][16]. Additionally, successful studies have been conducted on the partial replacement of coarse aggregates with ceramic tiles [9][10].

This paper will look into the partial substitution of coarse aggregate and cement in concrete with ceramic tiles and dolomite respectively. We will compare the effect of these substitutes to conventional concrete and look at how they affect the properties of the material.

2. Materials and method

2.1 Materials used

2.1.1 Concrete: For making concrete we are using Ordinary Portland cement (43 Grade), crushed stone (20mm) as coarse aggregate and M sand as fine aggregate. Water cement ratio is kept at 0.5. M20 mix design is used for the experiment. Mixing is done as per IS specification [11][12].

2.1.2 Dolomite powder: Dolomite is a substance that is extracted from sedimentary rock beds, sometimes referred to as Dolostone. Some of the characteristics of dolomite powder are comparable to those of cement. Concrete's cost can be reduced and its strength can be somewhat increased by using dolomite powder.

2.1.3 Ceramic tiles: Practically all constructions incorporate ceramic tiles as essential building materials. Natural materials are sintered at high temperatures to generate ceramic products. Ceramic tile is free of harmful compounds. Before utilizing the tiles in the experiment, they should be cleaned and dried out. The size of the broken ceramic tile should be greater than 4.75mm.

2.2 Methodology

This study's methodology is divided down into multiple steps. First, the dolomite and ceramic tiles waste materials are collected from the local sources. The desired-sized dolomite particles will be obtained by crushing and sieving the material. Additionally, to get the right-sized particles, the ceramic tiles will be crushed and sieved.

The basic properties of coarse aggregate, fine aggregate, and cement will be determined and a comparison will be made with the standard values [8][14]. Concrete cubes will be casted and it will be cured for 28 days. Next, the concrete mixtures are prepared with varying percentages of dolomite and ceramic tiles as partial replacements for cement and coarse aggregate respectively. Water - cement ratio is maintained at 0.5 for all mixes. The slump test will be performed to determine whether the combinations are workable.

After testing the workability of the mixtures, the concrete cubes are casted using the prepared mixtures. Each cube will be cured for a period of 28 days. After curing, the cubes are then tested for compressive strength with a compression testing machine. Finally, the results obtained from the tests are analyzed and compared to traditional concrete.

2.2 Experimental work

The concrete must be prepared with partial replacement additives. According to research investigations, concrete will have better strength if the dolomite is substituted by 10% [7]. Keeping the dolomite content constant at 10%, the concrete mix is prepared with coarse aggregate substituted in different ratios with ceramic tiles. The partial replacement percentages we adopted were 10%, 20%, and 30%. The mixes are tested for workability. Cubes are prepared and after 24 hours of setting time it will be cured for 28 days. Cubes are tested and compared to the standard values after 28 days of curing [13].

3. Results & discussions

3.1 Determination of basic properties

The basic properties are determined as per IS Standards and the results are obtained as follows:

Table 1: Basic Properties of ingredients

Specimen	Test	Value
Cement	Specific Gravity	3.1
	Initial Setting Time	60 mins
Coarse aggregate	Bulk Density	1474 kg/m ³
	% Air Voids	40.67 %
Fine aggregate	Specific Gravity	2.8
	Bulk Density	1723 kg/m ³
	% Air Voids	46.4 %
Concrete	Slump test	73

The results fall within the range of the standard values.

The concrete mix with coarse aggregate partially substituted by ceramic tiles at 10%, 20%, and 30% is designated as A1, A2, and A3, respectively. The standard mix with no replacement is designated as A.

3.2 Slump test

The slump test was performed as per IS Standards and the results are obtained as follows:

Table 2. Slump values of concrete in which dolomite and ceramic tile partially replaced

Mix	Dolomite Content (%)	Ceramic Tile Content (%)	Slump Value (mm)
A1	10	10	83
A2	10	20	80
A3	10	30	75

Figure 1. Comparison of slump values of different mixes

From the above chart, as the ceramic tile content is increased, a decrease in workability is observed. The workability of ceramic tile mix is lesser than the normal mix.

3.3 Compressive strength test

Table 3. Compressive strength values of concrete in N/mm² in which dolomite and ceramic tiles are partially replaced

Mix	Sample1	Sample2	Sample3
A	22.2	23.5	23.5
A1	21.3	21.7	21.3
A2	24.4	26.2	25.7
A3	24	24	24

Figure 2. Comparison of compressive strength of different mixes

From the above chart we can observe that when the percentage of ceramic tile increases by up to 20%, the compressive strength also increases. However, after 20%, the compressive strength continues to decline. Ceramic tile mixtures with 20% and 30% have a higher compressive strength than the normal mix.

4. Conclusion

The following conclusions were drawn in light of the investigation and experimental findings. The alternative materials can be effectively used as replacement of ingredients in concrete. Concrete's strength is observed to increase when dolomite and ceramic tiles were partially substituted for cement and coarse aggregate, respectively.

Taking the dolomite content of 10% as constant, the workability of concrete mix is decreasing as the ceramic tile content is increased. As per the compressive strength results of various mixes, the mix with 10% cement replacement with dolomite and 20% coarse aggregate replacement with ceramic tiles have more compressive strength than the standard mix.

By employing the ceramic waste in this project in a scientific manner, we can contribute to the sustainable growth of the building sector. We can thus resolve issues like the trash disposal dilemma by using this replacement method. In addition to saving money, adopting replacement materials facilitates the environmentally responsible disposal of these substitute components.

REFERENCES

- [1] Winnefeld, Frank & Leemann, Andreas & German, Alexander & Lothenbach, Barbara. (2022). CO₂ storage in cement and concrete by mineral carbonation. *Current Opinion in Green and Sustainable Chemistry*. 38. 100672. [10.1016/j.cogsc.2022.100672](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cogsc.2022.100672).
- [2] Dey, Ashish & Rumman, Rubaiya & Wakjira, Tadesse & Jindal, Ashish & Bediwy, Ahmed & Islam, M. & Alam, M. Shahria & Al-Martini, Samer & Sabouni, Reem. (2024). Towards net-zero emission: A case study investigating sustainability potential of geopolymer concrete with recycled glass powder and gold mine tailings. *Journal of Building Engineering*. 86. 108683. [10.1016/j.job.2024.108683](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.job.2024.108683).
- [3] Andrew, R. M.: Global CO₂ emissions from cement production, 1928–2018, *Earth System Science Data*, 11, 1675–1710, <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-11-1675-2019>, 2019.

- [4] Fateh Belaïd, How does concrete and cement industry transformation contribute to mitigating climate change challenges? *Resources, Conservation & Recycling Advances*, Volume 15, 2022, 200084, ISSN 2667-3789, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rcradv.2022.200084>.
- [5] Paul, S.C., Faruky, S.A.U., Babafemi, A.J. et al. Eco-friendly concrete with waste ceramic tile as coarse aggregate: mechanical strength, durability, and microstructural properties. *Asian J Civ Eng* 24, 3363–3373 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42107-023-00718-x>
- [6] Sivakumar, S. Srividhya, V. Sathiyamoorthy, M. Seenivasan, M.R. Subbarayan, Impact of waste ceramic tiles as partial replacement of fine and coarse aggregate in concrete, *Materials Today: Proceedings*, Volume 61, Part 2, 2022, Pages 224-231, ISSN 2214-7853, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2021.08.142>.
- [7] Pramod Dhamne | Dr. P. B. Nagarnaik "Experimental Investigation on Replacement of Cement in Concrete Partially by using Dolomite Powder" Published in *International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd)*, ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-3 | Issue-3, April 2019, pp.790-792, URL: <https://www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd23035.pdf>
- [8] IS 8112 (1989): Specification for 43 grade ordinary Portland cement [CED 2: Cement and Concrete]
- [9] Aruna D, Rajendra Prabhu, Subhash C Yaragal, Katta Venkata ramana, *IJRET*: eISSN: 2319-1163 | pISSN: 2321- 7308.
- [10] Batriti Monhun R. Marwein, M. Sneha, I. Bharathidasan *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, Volume 7, Issue 4, April-2016 ISSN 2229- 5518.
- [11] IS 10262 (2009): Guidelines for concrete mix design proportioning [CED 2: Cement and Concrete]
- [12] IS 456 (2000): Plain and Reinforced Concrete - Code of Practice [CED 2: Cement and Concrete]
- [13] IS 516:2018 compression test on cube
- [14] IS 2386-3 (1963): Methods of test for aggregates for concrete, Part 3: Specific gravity, density, voids, absorption and bulking [CED 2: Cement and Concrete]
- [15] Athulya Sugathan, "Experimental Investigation on partial Replacement of Cement with dolomite powder" *IJIRSET*, Vol. 6, Issue 7, July 2017
- [16] L.Ranjith Kumar, J.Kiran, P.Rangarajan, "Properties of Concrete Incorporating Dolomite Powder" *IOSR Journal of Mechanical and Civil Engineering*, Volume 14, Issue 2 Ver. II (March - April 2017), PP 78-80.